

Rac-4n

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-118-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	102	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 67 RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	5/16/2022 10:03:01 PM CST		
Date Processed:	5/16/2022 10:36:18 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.576	806014	51.02	62677
2	10.164	773847	48.98	45558

Asy-4n

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-118-asy-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	94	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 3 67 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	5/16/2022 9:43:32 PM CST		
Date Processed:	5/16/2022 10:30:00 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	7.561	23033819	89.75	1742933
2	10.160	2631074	10.25	168831